

Arulmigu Agatheeswarar Temple in Vikravandi, Villupuram District, Tamil Nadu- A Study

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the historical importance of Arulmigu Agatheeswarar Temple at Vikravandi in Villupuram District in Tamil Nadu. Tamil Nadu has been renowned as land of temple which depicted the culture and tradition of the nation and the people. The cultural attributes revealed in the form of constructing the temples especially the Hindu religion. Both kings and their royal member's eagerly constructed the temple to prove their attributes to the religion. Also they are donated the lands or kinds to the temple for the glorification. In Villupuram more than 65 temples belongs to Siva which glorified from archaic to modern period. This Agatheeswar temple eastern side of entrance, when we entered the temple the Sri Venkatesha perumal located in the opposite side. Sri Chandra God shrine located and the Surya god located the other side. In the northern side Sri Brama Swamy god located and Sri Vishnu Durga god faced in the northern side. This Temple belongs to eleventh century from Cholas which depicted from the epigraphical and sculptural sources.

Keywords : Agatheeswarar Temple, Hindu religion, Vishu Durga, Chola Period, Tree worship

Introduction

A dynamic role in all the significant aspects of human existence is recreated by the temple. In India, a temple is a place of worship for the overwhelming majority. Temples abound in India¹. The practice of worshipping trees², dates back to the Harappan era and has pan-Indian roots. Animism³ and ancestral worship⁴, two early forms of deity and goddess worship, developed during the Megalithic era. Further development of these concepts occurred in Tamil Nadu during the Sangam period. In comparison to earlier eras, religion played a more significant but harmonious role in Sangam society. The Sangam time is credited with constructing the temple architecture in Tamil Nadu. The writers of the Sangam delve into high esteem.⁵

Tamil Nadu has been renowned as land of temple which depicted the culture and tradition of the nation and the people. The cultural attributes revealed in the form of constructing the temples especially the Hindu religion. Both kings and their royal member's eagerly constructed the temple to prove their attributes to the religion. Also they are donated the lands or kinds to the temple for the glorification. On the path, the Chola were made tremendous contribution to the temple in South India. Villupuram has been renowned as *Nadu Nadu*, which acted as the prominent place where the religions like Buddhism, Jainism and Hinduism have glorified which witnessed the temple and beds. Also the literary sources authenticated the theory well. However, Hinduism survived more years which followed by the people more number. Both *Saivism* and *Vaisnavism* flourished in this land and depicted the temple equally well. Apart from this the minor deities also worshipped in this land. In Vikravandi there is lot of temple held which belongs to the major and minor temples. But some of them are glorified, some of them are neglected. Likewise, the Arulmigu Agatheeswarar temple has been forgotten by the historian. In this study has to reveal the significance of the temple to the world and its significance over the years. This article deals with the historical importance of Arulmigu Agatheeswarar Temple at Vikravandi in Villupuram District in Tamil Nadu.

Vikkiravandi

Arulmigu Agatheeswarar temple is located in Vikkiravandi taluk in Villupuram District. Vikravandi is located in the Villupuram taluq of the South Arcot district, on the ninety and

quarter miles from Chennai. The village is about a one kilometer distance from the railway station. The Agatheewar temple is located in Vikkiravandi at Villupuram. In Villupuram more than 64 temples belongs to Siva worship. Among them more than five were named Agatheeswarar temple. Geographical location of the district Villuppuram District lies between 11 38' 25" N and 12 20' 44" S: 78 15' 00" W and 79 42' 55" E with an area of 7194 sq. km It was carved out from the South Arcot District on 30.09.1993 and was rechristened as Villuppuram District. The residual part of the erstwhile South Arcot district was named as Cuddalore District. It is surrounded on East and South by Cuddalore District; the West by Salem and Dharmapuri districts and on the North by Thiruvannamalai and Kanchipuram districts.⁶

History of the Temple

Tamil Nadu is home to a vast array of temples that depict social, economic, and cultural developments from antiquity to the present. The temple may be a key entity in South Indian society's traditional path, describing social order, hegemony, and relationships. *Saivism* and *Vaishnavism* are the two main divisions of Hinduism. Vaishnavites are those who practice vaishnavism and venerate Lord Vishnu as their main deity. The Saiva movement's adherents, known as Shivaites, regard Lord Shiva as the ultimate deity. Under the Cholas, both *saivism* and *vaishnavism* may have thrived in South India. Thirunavalur is one of the sacred Saiva sites in Tamil Nadu and is located on the path. This chapter deals with the history of the temple both historical and mythological perspective.

Period

This Temple belongs to eleventh century from Cholas which depicted from the epigraphical and sculptural sources.⁷ This temple inscriptional data belong to Chola King Kulothunga was remarkable one. Also it revealed that this region has been called as 'Vikrama Pandiya Chadurvedi Mangalam'. Also there are some inscriptions existed from this temple from Sambhuvaraya and Vijayanaagar and Nayaks. There is another temple in Vikkiravandi might be significant belongs to thousand years old namely Varatharaja Perumal Temple. On the consequences, the Agastessaarar temple is also five hundred years old.

Sri Agatheeswarar

Rarely a living human can also receive such Easwar title due to their strong Agni puja towards Lord Kailasa Rudra Murthy. Examples are Agastheeswarar (saint Agasthiyar) and King Ravana(Ravan Eswar). Each Eswar god is an eternal human soul who obtained the divined title as Easwar from Lord Siva due to their sprit to Lord Siva in their human life. King Ravana;s wife Mandodhari was a sincere devotee of Lord Siva. Saint Agasthyar lived with his wife Lop Mudra. These women attained salvation and obtained the Easwar goddess title.

All Easwar gods have five elements cosmic energy handling powers, and hence they worshipped with Na Ma Si Ya Ya mantras and called Lord Siva. Some Rishi’s souls obtained their Easwar title from Adhi Paraasakthi, and they will reside in the Aadhi Parasakthi temple. These Easwar gods, Mahrishis, Brahma rishis and protective gods function as divine retinue under the command of Lord Kailasha Rudra Murthy. The aprivar gods and male protective gods under Easwar gods are also promoted as Easwar gods when such eternal souls exist for more than 2000 years and learned efficiently many cosmic energy handling skills in their eternal life.

Other than these Easwar gods who reside in siva temples, many souls of saints and rishis obtained Easwar titles still roaming around in deep forests/mountains etc., where abundant water, fire, and air cosmic energy exists. Such souls will be absorbing nature’s free –roaming energy particles and strenghtening their souls to keep their eternal life whenever any new Lord Siva or Easwar god’s temples are constructed, then highly skilled immortal human’s souls are appointed over there by the Lord Kailasha Rudra Muthey, and Nandi Easwar will supervise them. Such newly appointed souls will get the Easwar god title in that new Siva temple .Some of the eternal human souls could trigger the mind of some devotees, and hence such devotees constructed a Siva temple for an Easwar god. Thus, many Easwar god temples were constructed.

Similarly, many women, who worshipped Sri Parvathi Devi, obtained the Parivar goddess status through Saktham worship. Thus in each such Lord Siva Temple there will be Parivar Goddesses as Ambal, Amman, or Devi/Mata. They perform the divine responsibility of Sri parvathi Devi in that Lord Siva/Eswar temple. But they are not avatars of Sri Parvati Devi. They are independent female eternal souls.

All Easwar God temples have a considerable divine retinue, and hence many skilled godly souls reside over there. These temple are occupied with many parivar gods, protective gods, navagrahas, souls who obtained the Ganapathy and Murugar titles etc., the prime protective gods are Sri Bhariavar, Chandikeshwar, Veerabhadrar, Kali Devi etc. In some Siva or Easwar temples, the Navagrahas (nine planets) such as Saturn are worshipped as Sani Easwar in an exclusive moolasthanam where one of the godly souls who have cosmic skills to control the ill effects of the Saturn planet's cosmic energy resides and bless the devotees in that temple.

Lord Kailasa Rudra Muthry has a huge divine retinue under him. The first level parivar gods under Lord Kailasa Rudra Murthy are Easwar gods. Various Easwar titled gods reside at many temples, and they rule a vast cosmic zone around their temple and bless the worshippers of that area. In every god or Lord Siva temple, there will be one Easwar god residing in the *moolasthanam*, and under him, there are many souls that function as his parivar gods. These parivar gods live in small garba-grihas and are worshipped with divine titles such as Ganapathy, Murugar, chandikeshwar, Kala Bhairavar, Veera Badrar, Kali Devi, and various other Amman Goddesses. These parivar gods also reside in the *moolastahnam* of an independent temple and are worshipped as the temple's prime god.

The Temple and society

The temples played a significant role as tribunals of law, educational institutions, libraries, and public record offices, centres of art and culture, places of employment, places of commerce, banks, and feeding facilities. As a result, churches engaged in a variety of activities within and outside of their grounds. They offered assistance at different times throughout the day in a variety of ways. Numerous documents show that, aside from the Brahmanas, there were no educational opportunities available to the general public in these temples. However, everyone worked together to support and keep the customs alive. The temples provided for the people's spiritual and intellectual development in addition to their physical requirements. The lower caste men had their part in manual labor, while the upper caste men had a larger pay role in spiritual and educational matters. This chapter sheds light on the temple's numerous activities, specifically its societal, social life, and cultural pursuits. The temples served as both sites of worship and strong social institutions. The locals gave their complete support in the establishment of the

temples as corporations. Thiruthondishwara temple at Thirunavalur has inscriptions that explain the social structure of the time. They enjoyed a devoted patronage from the ruling Kings⁸, their subordinates⁹ and the public. Thus the social life of the Tamils centered on the temples. Therefore the temples played significant role in the social life of the people¹⁰.

Temple and Economy condition

The temples have played an important part in the economic life of the people. Every big temple has been a wealthy institution owing vast properties in land. As the biggest landlord, the temples have employed a large number of laborers. They have cultivated lands, besides encouraging rural activities, like extension of cultivation and rehabilitation of village. Every temple has been a huge consumer and has purchased various articles of purposes of conducting worship. The temples were generally wealthy and the wealth of the South Indian temples was a wonder to foreign travelers in medieval times. The wealth of the temple made of royal endowments, and benefactions by the public. Endowments were usually known as *Bramadeya* or *Devadana* lands. The kings patronized temples by either making grants of lands tam-free or at low quit-rent to enjoy by them in perpetuity, or by making over specified taxes of their areas in which the temple was situated. Endowments were also made for specific purpose, as for the repair of a portion of the temple or the institution of a service in the name of the donor, costly Jewelry was presented to the temples and provisions were made for some services by the dedication of few cow and sheep.

Architecture

One of the most imperishable attainments of Indian civilization is undeniably its architecture. The artistic and architectural heritage of India is almost five millennia old.¹¹ This agatheeswarar is built the best architecture is by placing marble stones of each other and with limestone powder. This temple was built in this manner. The artists worked very hard to build the temple. This temple is the best architecture style by carving stones. The artists worked hard to build in this temple. This temple build in the 19th century by black stones and Chunnam . This temple made of cast iron and the stone.¹²The Temple has sanctum *sanctorum*, *antarla*, *artha mandapam* and a *mukha mandapam*. The adhistana is with jagathy, virutha kumuda, kandam,

kapotham with nasi kood, yazhivari (Vyazha vari). The sanctum walls are supported with Vishnu kanda pilasters and virutha pilastes. The uniqueness of this temple is above the kalasam of the pillar, kumbam, pali, palakai veer kandam tharanga pothyal, prastaram, mathalam in valbi and vimana are built with brick.

Temple style

Nagara type of North Indian temple has curvilinear towers. They have square base. Dravidian type South India has towers like pyramids. They have octagonal base. Vesara type of Temples combined both styles. They have circular base. Earlier temples were building by perishable materials such as wood, brick, clay and mortar. Then Guptas made temples with caves. The gigantic temples were building from 8th century A.D. In South India Pandyas and Pallavas made cave temples from sixth century C.E at Kazugumalai, Kanchi and Mamallapuram.¹³

Structure of the temple

This Agatheeswar temple eastern side of entrance, when we entered the temple the Sri Venkatesha perumal sami located in the opposite side. In rightern side the Sri Chandra God shrine located and the Surya god located the other side. In the northern side Sri Bramma Swamy god located and Sri Vishnu Durga god faced in the northern side. The righter side and southern side Sri Kandikeshwarar shrine located. Sri Sorna Bhaiavar god located on the western side which faced towards the western side.

The temple have navagriha shrine in the temple premises. Sri Agatheeswar temple is having Sri Nandigeshwarar on the central part of the temple. Sri Subramaniya god is facing towards the eastern side and Sri Valli on the leftern side and Sri Theivanai located on the righter side of the Lord Subramaniam. The central part of the temple Sri Dharma Sasta was located, and Sri Baladhadayuthapani is located in the eastern side of the temple. Eastern side of the temple, Sri Dharma Sasta is located, and eastern side of the temple Sri Balathandayuthapani located. Sri Raja Vinayagar is located in the opposite direction towards the temple. The mandabam is built in

the temple's barrier. The temple is having the odd side and animal inscriptions. The most important part of this temple is Sri Dharmatata Pavardini shrine inside the temple.

The marriage is conducted in the middle of the temple, such programme having dancing with the stage. The stage is there conducting programmes many around the temple. There are bugs. Sri Selva Vinayagar is located on the left side of the temple facing south, while entering the left side of the temple. Srihdassani murthy is situated as seen from the side.

On the left side of the temple is a madapalli where the items are collected. In the middle of the temple there is a well called for taking tears. Nearby epigram and Arasanam are both good condition. The temple is surrounding walls are in are in place. The Karuvai Artha mandabam of Moolavar sannadi is in the wide area of main Mugamandapan and appall sannandi also three. Secrets are seen in the temple, considering the antiquity and security of the temple. The colour is experience is removed.

Conclusion

If there is a need, the damaged mathalin can be plastered and fixed without affecting the stability of the temple. It can be arranged in different ways. As the plants in the front porch are kept in an unsightly condition they should be repaired immediately. The ancestor of this built with seeds. Ammal sannadi sandishur sanndai, navagraha can be repaired to avoid damage old parts. The temple needs a lot of repairs to the undamaged parts considering the ancient architecture. The architecture and inscriptions repairs will antiquity of and the above mentioned affect the antiquity of the temple safeguarded.¹⁴

In Villupuram more than 65 temples belongs to Siva which glorified from archaic to modern period. People have worshipped the lord every day thrice through pujas. Also they have worshipped the lord for celebrated through the festivals in this region. Indeed, temple is the prominent place always interconnected with the people in of places were damaged by the nature, and bushed. Some of them are looked in to the dial pated condition. The HRNC was conducted the survey to the temple and made some modification for the same. But this ancient treasure was

damaged and loss its heritage through the natural disaster. Hence, the Government and the temple authorities and the people who made necessary steps to save the heritage monument.

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